

PARENTING STYLES AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL 3 (JSS 3) IN AWKA NORTH L. G. A., ANAMBRA STATE

Chikendu Rebecca Ebonam Ph.D and Ajakor Florence Ratanna

Department of Science Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Email: re.chikendu@unizik.edu.ng and ajakor.fr@unizik.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14283408>

Abstract: This study ascertained the effect of parenting styles on academic performance among Junior Secondary School 3 (JSS 3) students in Awka North Local Government Area (LGA), Anambra State. A survey research design was employed, targeting 7,943 JSS 3 students in 10 government secondary schools. A sample of 150 respondents was randomly selected from five schools. Data were analyzed with Pearson's correlation, linear regression, and Regression ANOVA at a 0.05 significance level. The results provide insights into the parenting styles prevalent in the region and their correlation with students' academic achievement. The results revealed that permissive styles have negative relationships, while uninvolved parenting style showed no significant impact. Based on the findings, it is recommended that parents adopt authoritative parenting styles to provide supportive environments for their children. Schools should also organize workshops to educate parents on effective parenting practices. By adopting positive parenting strategies, parents can significantly enhance their children's academic achievement and overall well-being.

Keywords: Parenting styles, Permissive styles, Uninvolved parenting style and Academic performance

Introduction

Parenting styles may lead to the low or high academic performance of the child. Students who come from parenting styles that guides them by engaging with their education are likely to achieve higher grades than their mates. Thus, the academic performance of students depends much on the parenting styles exhibited in the family. Parents are expected to impact in their children value for hard work and love for learning which eventually translates to good academic results. When parents reinforce what teachers do, students tend to do well in school and achieve higher academically. Permissive parents are very lenient, nurturing and responsive to their child's emotional needs. They often avoid setting boundaries or consequences, which can lead to children lacking self-discipline and responsibility (Hoskin, 2014).

The uninvolved parents' also known as neglectful parents ignore their children, who receive little guidance, nurturing, and parental attention. They don't set rules or expectations, and they tend to have minimal knowledge about what their children are doing. They don't devote much time or energy to meeting children's basic needs (Edmund, 2014). At times, uninvolved parents lack knowledge about child development and academic

performance. They often believe that their child will do better without their oversight. Parenting styles could therefore be an influential factor in the academic performance of a student for they play a vital role in helping or hindering academic success.

Academic failure on the other hand brings forth a share of negative consequences as the student is likely to miss out on life opportunities. Studies have shown that although other factors influence academic performance, parenting is deemed to have a more lasting impact and the success of parenting can be reflected in a child's academic outcome (Checa & Gutierrez 2018).

From the aforesaid, it is presumed that a student's academic outcome does not only depend on what is happening in the school but also has a lot to do with interaction with their parents and the kind of parenting style exercised in their family. Therefore, the relationship between parenting styles and academic performance remains a critical debate, hence the researchers want to examine parenting styles as it correlates to upper basic education students' academic performance in basic science in Awka North.

This study ascertained the effect of parenting styles on students' academic performance in basic science in Awka North Local Government Area. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The relationship between permissive parenting style and student's academic performance in Basic Science.
2. The relationship between uninvolved parenting style and student's academic performance in Basic Science.

Literature Review

Permissive Parenting style and Academic Performance

According to Hoskins (2014), permissive parents can be characterized as exhibiting low level of demandingness and high level of responsiveness. They behave in a manner that is more affirmative toward the impulses, actions and desires of adolescent while consulting with them about family decisions. In addition, they tend to avoid engaging in behavioral control, do not set rules and set a small number of behavioral expectations for their adolescents. From this perspective, it can be stated that permissive parents actually allow the child to actively participate without being concerned for their actions.

Permissive parents tend to be warm, nurturing and usually have minimal or no expectations. They impose limited rules on their children. Communication remains open, but parents allow their children to figure things out for themselves. These low levels of expectation usually result in rare uses of discipline. They act more like friends than parents. Limited rules can lead to children with unhealthy habits both in eating, bedtime, screen time, and when to do their homework. Freedom to this degree can lead to other negative habits as the parent does not provide much guidance on moderation. Technically, the academic performance of children of permissive parenting suffers setback as result of excessive freedom and lack of guidance.

Uninvolved Parenting style and Academic Performance

Uninvolved parenting style is neither demanding nor responsive. It is also called neglectful parenting. The parents are low in warmth and control, and are generally not involved in their child's life, are disengaged, undemanding, low in responsiveness, and do not set limits (Edmund, 2015).

Uninvolved parenting can also mean dismissing the children's emotions and opinions. Parents are emotionally unsupportive of their children, but will still provide their basic needs. Children whose parents are neglectful develop the sense that other aspects of the parents' lives are more important than they are. Many children of this

parenting style often attempt to provide for themselves or halt depending on the parent to get a feeling of being independent and mature beyond their age (Edmund, 2015). There is low level of academic performance from children of uninvolved parents.

Parenting Style and Student's Academic Performance

Most parents are constantly concerned about their children's success, whether academics, arts, sports or any other interest the child might have. Most parents want to help their children reach their full potential. Some parents become very intentional about propelling their kids into success, some are too busy to create healthy and friendly environment for their wards and some find it more useful to have a relaxed attitude about it.

Lack of family and parental support, good educative environment, and good parenting relationship can pose a lot of psychological problems to a child. It can also limit the academic performance and success of the child.

Where parent-child interaction is high as a result of healthy parenting, the child is likely to work hard academically even in the absence of support. Parenting style revolving around warm attention and support, significantly and positively predicts the academic performance and success of a child.

A positive parenting style such as acceptance, support, and emotional warmth facilitates the development of high self-esteem in children in basic science classes.

Empirical Studies

Vera, Idiahi, and Osagie (2020) evaluated the parenting styles as a correlate of academic motivation among secondary adolescents in Edo state. Correlational research design was employed. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw up a sample consisting of 936 SS2 in-school adolescents of both gender; 468 males and 468 females. Parenting style self-report inventory scale (PSSIS) and Academic motivation self-report inventory (AMSI) were administered on students to collect data for the study. The research questions were answered with Pearson "r" statistic while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that authoritarian parenting style is the most commonly practiced parenting style in families. There is a significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic motivation among female in-school adolescents. Ishola and Taiwo (2015) examined the parenting styles and academic performance of social science students in junior secondary schools in Ilorin South Local Government Area, Kwara State. Correlational research design was employed. Data collection was done through the use of questionnaire. Data collected was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC). Findings from the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of male students in social studies, while there was no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of female students in social studies. Mumina et al (2022) ascertained the relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of secondary school students in public and private schools in Lamu County, Kenya. Correlational survey and phenomenological research designs were employed. Data collection was done using questionnaire while data obtained were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The findings of the study revealed that there was a weak, negative and significant relationship between uninvolved parenting style, permissive parenting style and academic performance. The relationship between the previous research and the current study is that both of them used questionnaire for data collection but differs from each other in terms of location.

Research and Methodology

Surveys are also excellent vehicles for the measurement of attitudes and orientation prevalent within a large population. Survey method is therefore found the most appropriate in this study.

The target population of the study consist of 7943 JSS 3 students in the ten (10) government secondary schools in Awka North LGA of Anambra State. (PPSSC 2023)

The sample size for this study is 150 respondents. This figure was considered adequate considering the available resources and time to the researcher. The sample size was drawn using multiple sampling techniques which includes: Firstly, 5 schools were selected out of the 10 government secondary schools by balloting. All 10 secondary schools were written down, mixed, and then randomly selected. Secondly, 150 JSS 3 students were selected from the 5 selected secondary schools by assigning unique IDs to each student, and randomly selecting 150 students from the list using random number generation.

Instrument for Data Collection

The researcher used questionnaire as the instrument for the data collection which were made up of questions arranged systematically based on the research questions to collect data and information from the students of basic science in 5 selected schools in the area of study.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was questionnaire. The researchers personally administered the instrument on the respondents. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents in the sampled schools. A total of 150 questionnaires were given to the respondents and all were collected on the spot to avoid loss of any.

Method of Analysis

The r^2 (coefficient of determination) and r (Pearson’s correlation) and linear regression analyses were used to analyze the data and draw conclusions. A 3-way guide was used for interpreting r as follows: 0.00 – 0.30 (correlation is low), 0.31- 0.79 (correlation is moderate), 0.80 and above (correlation is high). At a significance level of 0.05, simple linear regression (Regression ANOVA) were used to test Hypotheses. The analysis was done using SPSS Version 25.

Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between permissive parenting style and students’ academic performance in basic science?

Table 1: Regression analysis of the relationship between permissive parenting style and students’ academic performance in basic science

Model	r	r^2	Adjusted r^2	Std. Error of the Estimate	Decision
1	-.365 ^a	.133	.127	11.65780	Moderate negative relationship

a. Predictors: (Constant), Permissive

The result in Table 5 shows that the correlation coefficient between permissive parenting style and student’s academic performance in basic science is -.365. This indicates that there exists a moderate negative relationship between permissive parenting style and students’ academic performance in basic science. The data in the table also revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of -.365 is .133. The coefficient of determination (r^2) indicates that 13.3% variation in students’ academic performance in Basic Science can be attributed to permissive parenting style. Furthermore, hypothesis three below was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to determine if there is any significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students’ academic performance in basic science.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science

Table 2: ANOVA Regression analysis on significance of the relationship between permissive parenting style on students' academic performance in basic science

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3090.623	1	3090.623	22.741	.000 ^b
	Residual	20113.837	148	135.904		
	Total	23204.460	149			

a. Dependent Variable: BSAS

b. Predictors: (Constant), Permissive

The result in table 6 shows that at 22.741 F-value the probability value of .000 was obtained which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is a significant negative relationship ($P < 0.05$) between permissive parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science. This implies that as permissive parenting style is increasing students' academic performance in basic science will be decreasing and vice versa.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science?

Table 3: Regression analysis of the relationship between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science

Model	r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Decision
1	.074 ^a	.005	-.001	12.48750	Low positive relationship

a. Predictors: (Constant), Uninvolved

The result in Table 7 shows that the correlation coefficient between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science is .074. This indicates that there exists a low positive relationship between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science. The data in the table also revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of .074 is .005. The coefficient of determination (r^2) indicates that 0.5% variation in students' academic performance in Basic Science can be attributed to uninvolved parenting style. Furthermore, hypothesis four below was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to determine if there is any significant relationship between uninvolved parenting style and student's academic performance in basic science.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science.

Table 4: ANOVA Regression analysis on significance of the relationship between uninvolved parenting style on students' academic performance in basic science

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	125.689	1	125.689	.806	.371 ^b
	Residual	23078.771	148	155.938		
	Total	23204.460	149			

a. Dependent Variable: BSAS

b. Predictors: (Constant), Uninvolved

The result in table 8 shows that at .806 F-value the probability value of .371 was obtained which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, there is no significant relationship ($P>0.05$) between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science. This implies that uninvolved parenting style does not make any significant contribution on students' academic performance in basic science.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science?

Table 5: Regression analysis of the relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science

Model	r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Decision
1	-.316 ^a	.100	.094	11.87957	Moderate negative relationship

a. Predictors: (Constant), Parenting Styles

The result in Table 9 shows that the correlation coefficient between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science is -.316. This indicates that there exists a moderate negative relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science. The data in the table also revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of -.316 is .100. The coefficient of determination (r^2) indicates that 10.0% variation in students' academic performance in Basic Science can be attributed to parenting styles. Furthermore, hypothesis five below was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to determine if there is any significant relationship between parenting styles and student's academic performance in basic science.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant relationship between parenting styles on students' academic performance in basic science.

Table 6: ANOVA Regression analysis on significance of the relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2318.094	1	2318.094	16.426	.000 ^b
	Residual	20886.366	148	141.124		
	Total	23204.460	149			

a. Dependent Variable: BSAS

b. Predictors: (Constant), Parenting Styles

The result in table 10 shows that at 16.426 F-value the probability value of .000 was obtained which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is a significant negative relationship ($P<0.05$) between parenting styles and student's academic performance in basic science. This implies that parenting styles is significantly related to students' academic performance in basic science, even though there is a negative relationship.

4.2 Discussion of the Findings

The relationship between permissive parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science

The findings of the study showed that there is a significant negative relationship between permissive parenting style and student's academic performance in basic science. This implies that as permissive parenting style is increasing students' academic performance in basic science will be decreasing and vice versa. This finding is in agreement with Fletcher & Powell (2016) who concluded that permissive parenting undermines adolescent self-regulation and self-motivation in learning. Permissive parenting style lacks monitoring and supervision which contributed to low academic performance of students. Findings from this study also replicates a study by Kosterelioglu (2018) who recounted that permissive parenting style had a negative impact on learning avoidance orientation with a low-level positive relationship to academic performance. In addition, Lindsay et al. (2018) confirm that permissive parents are non-protective of their children; they do not care how the children are doing either socially or academically. With the trend of parents keeping aloof from the academic welfare of the students, the result is that students are likely to lose track of their studies and eventually post poor results.

The relationship between uninvolved parenting style and students' academic performance in basic science

The findings of the study showed that there is no significant relationship between uninvolved parenting style and student's academic performance in basic science. This implies that uninvolved parenting style does not make any significant contribution on students' academic performance in basic science. This finding is in agreement with Aunola et al. (2014) who concluded that uninvolved parents' lack of involvement and monitoring do not directly impact academic achievement. However, it may indirectly affect academic performance through reduced parental support and increased behavioral problems.

The relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science

The findings of the study showed that the relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in basic science which is significant and moderately negative. This implies that parenting styles is significantly related to students' academic performance in basic science, even though there is a negative relationship. This is in line with the finding of Nwune and Anidi, (2021) and Imran, Kakar and Yousaf (2020) which implies that there is significant relationship between parenting styles and student's academic achievement. The findings of this study also support the findings of Baji and Mohammed (2015) revealing that there is a positive correlation existing between parenting styles and academic performance of JSS 3 students in Niger State.

Parenting styles affect children's academic performance differently. While it may affect some either positively or negatively, it may not affect some at all. Rochette and Bernier 2014 concludes that parents who use authoritarian parenting style combined with permissive parenting style result in worse academic performance of their children compared to those who use authoritative parenting style in combination with permissive parenting style. Usually, authoritative parents give stability and support their children's academic achievement, and emphasize the significance of education in a way that helps develop their children to become successful and responsible citizens.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of secondary school students in Basic Science. The findings revealed that permissive parenting styles have negative relationships. Uninvolved parenting style showed no significant relationship.

The study emphasizes the importance of positive parenting practices, such as parental involvement, reinforcement and motivation in fostering academic success. It also highlights the need for parents to adopt authoritative parenting styles providing a supportive and guided environment for their children. Positive parenting is required for early cognitive development, emotional balance, and good academic performance of students. While negative and hostile parenting leads to low academic performance of students. Hence, the later should be avoided.

Recommendations

Based on the

1. Parents' resource centers should be opened in individual schools with accessible local public library and information technology communication to boost school-parents' communication for permissive parenting.
2. Parents must be educated on the impact the parenting style they adopt in raising their children have on their academic performance and should thus adopt styles that can lend themselves in improving the cognitive, emotional, social and academic competencies of their children.

References

- Baji, M., & Mohammed, A. (2015). Relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of junior secondary school students in Niger State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 4(2), 1-9.
- Checa, I. C., & Gutierrez, M. (2018). Parenting styles and academic achievement: A study of Spanish adolescents. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 27(10), 2819-2828.
- Edmund, A. (2014). Uninvolved parenting style: A study of its effects on adolescents. *Journal of Family Issues*, 35(14), 3510-3532.
- Hoskin, D. (2014). Permissive parenting style: A study of its effects on children's academic achievement. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 3(1), 1-11.
- Ishola, A., & Taiwo, J. (2015). Parenting styles and academic performance of social science students in junior secondary schools in Ilorin South Local Government Area, Kwara State. *Journal of Educational Research*, 10(1), 12-20.
- Imran, M. J., Kakar, K., & Yousaf, M. (2020). Effect of parenting styles on academic performance of disabled students in Quetta, Pakistan. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 7(3), 062-069. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2020.7.3.0324>

- Kosterelioglu, I. (2018). Effects of parenting style on students' achievement goal orientation: A study on high school students. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 13(4), 91-107. <https://doi.org/10.29329/epasr.2018.178.5>
- Lindsay, A., Wasserman, M., Muñoz, M., Wallington, S., & Greane, M. (2018). Examining influences of parenting styles and practices on physical activity and sedentary behaviors in Latino children in the United States: Integrative review. *Public Health*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.2196/publichealth.8159>
- Mumina, A., Mwakaba, S., & Mwema, M. (2022). Relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of secondary school students in public and private schools in Lamu County, Kenya. *Journal of Educational Research*, 15(1), 1-12.
- Nwune, E. C., & Anidi, A. C. (2021). Parenting styles as a correlate of academic achievement of primary school pupils in Awka South. *Journal Plus Education*, 28(1), 30-38. Retrieved from <https://www.journalplusedu.com>
- Rochette, É., & Bernier, A. (2014). Parenting, family socioeconomic status, and child executive functioning: A longitudinal study. *Merrill-Palmer Quarterly*, 60(4), 431-460.
- Vera, C., Idiahi, I., & Osagie, J. (2020). Parenting styles as correlates of academic motivation among secondary adolescents in Edo State. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychology*, 12(1), 1-10.